

GAS FLOW PATHS IN CARBON / POLYMER COMPOSITES SUBJECT TO LN₂ AND COMBINED LN₂ AND 177 °C CYCLING

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Abstract: The distribution of ply-level micro-cracks in carbon / polymer composites was determined as a function of cryogenic cycling. IM7 / 977-2 carbon / epoxy, IM7 / 5250-4 carbon / bismaleimide, and IM7 / 3K e-beam cured carbon / epoxy cross-ply ([0/90]_{2S}) and quasi-isotropic ([0/45/-45/90]_S) laminates were tested for up to 1000 cycles. The thermal cycles consisted of either submersion in liquid nitrogen (LN₂) or a combined cycle consisting of equilibrating periods in LN₂, at room temperature, and at 177 °C. Several interesting trends were noticeable. Reducing the ply thickness by 30% in the IM7 / 5250-4 delayed surface ply micro-cracking by up to 200 cycles, but by 1000 cycles the surface ply micro-crack densities were nearly equal regardless of the ply thickness. Sectioning and polishing revealed greater micro-crack densities 2.5 cm away from the sample edges than at the edges several plies of each laminate. Finally, the addition of a hold of 5 minutes per cycle at the maximum service temperature (177 °C) increased the micro-crack density in all plies of the IM7 / 5250-4 laminates a minimum of 2 times and by 400 cycles had produced micro-cracks in every ply of the [0/+45/-45/90]_S laminate.

Key Words: Cryogenic cycling, carbon fiber, bismaleimide, micro-cracking, permeability

INTRODUCTION

Carbon / polymer composites are candidates for launch vehicle applications such as cryogenic tanks and fuel lines because of their high specific strength and the possibility of using unique and low cost fabrication techniques available for composites [1, 2]. However, for these applications the combination of cryogenic exposure during launch and elevated temperature exposure upon reentry (for reusable vehicles) combined with mechanical loading could produce significant damage accumulation that has been shown to alter mechanical [3] and permeability properties [4, 5]. Studies on cryogenic cycling of polymer composites to date have focused on many factors contributing to damage initiation and accumulation such as the number of cycles, the effect of the cycle temperature profile [6, 7], the resulting laminate permeability [4], and the damage initiation locations and growth pattern [8, 9]. Past cycling work has included experiments on materials similar to or the same as were tested for this paper [10]. For example, Kessler, *et al.* [8] cycled IM7 / 977-2 with a combined cycle of cool-down to -243 °C and warm up to 127 °C. Quasi-isotropic laminates did not micro-crack after ten cycles, and their mechanical properties and permeability were unaffected. Bechel, *et al.* [11] cycled various laminates of IM7 / 5250-4 at -196 °C (the temperature of LN₂) and found that the surface plies micro-cracked up to 42 times more than inner plies and did *not* saturate after 400 cycles. Combined reduced and elevated and temperature cycling studies have also been conducted [12] but are less common. For example, Henaff-Gardin, *et al.* [13] cycled T300 / 914 carbon / epoxy cross-ply laminates between -196 °C and several temperatures ranging from 20 °C to 130 °C. X-radiography indicated that higher temperatures resulted in more micro-cracks forming after fewer cycles.

This work extends the LN₂ cycling work of Bechel, *et al.* [11] by cycling IM7 / 5250-4 beyond 400 cycles to 1000 cycles and cycling IM7 / 977-2 to 1000 cycles so a comparison of micro-crack development in a medium temperature carbon / epoxy can be made with a high temperature carbon / bismaleimide with

similar structural properties [14]. A third material – IM7 / 3K – was cycled in LN₂ and added to the comparison because it was expected to have extremely low residual stress at room temperature due to e-beam curing. Finally, a hold of +177 °C was added to the cycling of IM7 / 5250-4 to simulate possible structural heating during atmospheric reentry. In general, this data may aid in the basic understanding of damage development in composites, but also may be useful for future analytical work aimed at predicting initiation and growth of micro-cracks that can cause gas flow through the wall of a composite vessel used to contain a cryogen.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus

The cycling apparatus consisted of an aluminum frame used to support and guide a sample container in vertical movement between positions inside a dewar of LN₂, in ambient air, and inside an oven (Figure 1). The sample container was attached to a hollow aluminum bar that was actuated at 6 cm /sec by a four phase, 10 V / phase stepper motor. In order to allow unattended operation a computer controlled the experiment by monitoring micro-switches and the revolutions of the motor. The 14 gage copper wire and galvanized steel mesh sample container had a capacity of up to eighteen 50.8 mm long by 50.8 mm wide samples spaced at 6.4 mm intervals. To reduce the time required for the samples to return to ambient temperature an 8 cm diameter fan was used to force ambient air across the sample container during periods when the samples were held outside the LN₂ and the oven.

Figure 1 Cryogenic / elevated temperature cycling apparatus

A solenoid valve electrically controlled by a temperature sensor made from a silicon transistor maintained the LN₂ level. In operation, as the liquid level fell, the transistor warmed and its base-emitter voltage rose triggering the solenoid. A 46 cm tall custom 1000 W convection oven located on the frame above the ambient air fan provided the elevated portion of the thermal cycle. The bottom of the oven (facing the LN₂ dewar) contained a 16 cm diameter opening for the sample container to pass through, and the oven

top face contained a 4 cm diameter opening for the actuation bar to pass through. As with the top of the LN₂ dewar, the oven openings remained open during operation. A fan inside the oven was positioned to minimize the loss of heat through the openings by forcing the oven airflow perpendicular to the openings. To avoid the reduced temperature near the oven bottom opening, the sample container was positioned inside the oven more than 10 cm from the bottom opening when heating.

Materials

Materials and lay-ups were chosen to study the effects of ply thickness, lay-up, and residual stresses due to a range of cure temperatures on damage accumulation. The cryogenic cycling was conducted on three materials. The first material was a composite consisting of medium stiffness IM7 carbon fibers from Hexcel and a high temperature (177 °C) bismaleimide matrix (5250-4 from Cytec-Fiberite) fabricated from standard thickness prepreg with a single ply thickness of 0.14 mm. The same material was also fabricated from a second prepreg with a less common thickness (but still commercially available) that resulted in a ply thickness of 0.21 mm. These two prepreps were the only ones available for this project, but were sufficient to demonstrate the micro-cracking trends as a function of ply thickness.

The second material consisted of IM7 fibers and a medium temperature (120 °C) toughened epoxy matrix (977-2 from Cytec- Fiberite). This material had a single ply thickness of 0.13 mm similar to the standard-ply-thickness IM7 / 5250-4. The third material consisted again of IM7 fibers and a different toughened epoxy matrix (3K from UCB Chemical) fabricated from standard thickness prepreg (0.13 mm). Unlike the first 2 materials that were autoclave cured at elevated temperature, the IM7 / 3K was e-beam cured at ambient temperature. [0/90]_{2S} and [0/+45/-45/90]_S laminates were fabricated from each of these materials. Three to five samples 50.8 mm x 50.8 mm were cut with the fibers in the 0° plies parallel to one polished side of the sample (Side A) and the fibers in the 90° plies parallel to the other polished side (Side B) for each material / lay-up combination. The laminates were laid up by hand and autoclave or e-beam cured according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

Cycle Dwell Times / Micro-Crack Density Measurements

To determine the minimum hold times necessary, temperature measurements were made using a 0.102 mm thick k-type thermocouple bonded between two 1.040 mm thick laminates of carbon / epoxy with a 0.203 mm layer of Epon 828. The times necessary for the center ply of this sample to reach the required temperatures (within 5 °C) were recorded when the sample was submerged in LN₂, placed in the oven at 177 °C, and warmed up or cooled down to room temperature (RT). Based on these measurements, a cycle of 2 minutes in the LN₂ followed by 5 minutes at RT was used for the IM7 / 5250-4 thick prepreg, IM7 / 5250-4 standard prepreg, IM7 / 977-2, and IM7 / 3K samples. Separate IM7 / 5250-4 standard prepreg samples were subject to a combined cycle consisting of 2 minutes in LN₂ followed by 5 minute holds at RT, 177 °C, and again at RT. Note, the 177 °C oven temperature is the maximum hot / wet service temperature for IM7 / 5250-4.

Each laminate was polished to a 0.2 μm finish on two perpendicular sides prior to cycling, and ply-level cracks were observed on the sample edge at 200X in an optical microscope. A crack was included in the micro-crack density measurement if it extended vertically (through the ply thickness) more than three-fourths through the ply. Cracks were counted after, 0, 1, 5, 15, 30, 75, 125, 250, 325, 400, 500, 650, 800, and 1000 cycles. The micro-crack densities for the 90° and 0° plies are the average of the micro-crack density over the 50.8 mm span on Side A and Side B, respectively, for 3-5 samples of each laminate (see Figure 2). The micro-crack densities of plies symmetric about the center of the laminate were averaged. For example, the micro-crack density of plies 1 and 8 were averaged, and plies 2 and 7 were averaged. The micro-crack densities for the +45° and -45° plies were obtained with the same averaging method but a separate result is reported for each of Side A and Side B since micro-cracks in the +45° and -45° plies

are visible on both sides. In addition, the IM7 / 5250-4 thick prepreg and IM7 / 5250-4 standard prepreg materials were sectioned after 1000 cycles (shown schematically in Figure 3) to measure micro-crack density away from the edges of the samples. Sides A' and B' were polished with the same procedure as Sides A and B, and the sectioned samples were placed for 30 minutes in a sonic cleaner to remove debris from the micro-cracks and to aid micro-crack identification. The micro-crack densities for each ply of each laminate, as observed on the sample edges, are plotted in Figures 4 to 7 as a function of cycles, and the sectioning results are in Tables 1 and 2. In Figures 4 to 7, "(LN₂/177°C)" refers to the combined cycle and "(=0)" indicates that no micro-cracks developed at any time through 1000 cycles.

Figure 2 Micro-crack density measurement areas

Figure 3 Sectioning process for IM7 / 5250-4

CRYOGENIC ONLY CYCLING

Carbon / Bismaleimide (IM7 / 5250-4)

The IM7 / 5250-4 surface ply micro-crack densities (plies 1 and 8) were considerably greater than for the inner plies – presumably due to thermal shock when the surface plies contacted the LN₂. The surface plies micro-crack densities in the thick prepreg samples reached substantial values (1.41 and 0.39 micro-cracks / cm) by 175 cycles while significant micro-cracking was delayed until 325 cycles in the standard prepreg samples. However, after 400 cycles the surface ply micro-crack density in the standard prepreg samples increased quicker until both laminates of the standard prepreg samples had equaled the micro-crack density in the [0/+45/-45/90]_s thick samples (5.6 micro-cracks / cm) by 1000 cycles. The surface ply micro-crack densities did not saturate even after 1000 cycles, nor did the rate of micro-crack initiation in the standard prepreg samples decrease. Consistent trends for the inner plies are more difficult to identify. Plies 2 and 7 had no micro-cracks except on Side B of the [0/+45/-45/90]_s samples in which it appeared that the earlier formation of surface ply cracks in the thick prepreg samples led to earlier micro-cracking (400 cycles) and greater numbers of plies 2 and 7 micro-cracks (0.85 vs. 0.07 micro-cracks / cm

at 1000 cycles). Plies 4 and 5 had no micro-cracks in the thicker samples while in plies 4 and 5 of the standard prepreg samples the micro-crack density remained less than 0.2 micro-cracks / cm through 1000 cycles. Since the laminates had no micro-cracks in plies 3 and 6, there were no complete paths through the thickness of these samples. In fact, 6 of the 8 plies remained intact in the thick prepreg samples.

Figure 4 Plies 1 and 8 edge micro-crack densities

Figure 5 Plies 2 and 7 edge micro-crack densities

Figure 6 Plies 3 and 6 edge micro-crack densities

Figure 7 Plies 4 and 5 edge micro-crack densities

The micro-crack densities observed midway between the edges of the samples are listed in Tables 1 and 2. In the IM7 / 5250-4 laminates the micro-crack densities in the surface plies were greater at the mid-span than at the edges. For example, the mid-span micro-crack density was 9% greater for thick prepreg $[0/90]_{2S}$ and 36% greater for standard prepreg $[0/+45/-45/90]_{2S}$. Theoretically, if the micro-cracks in the surface plies initiated at the sample edges and tended to propagate across the width toward the middle of

the sample, the micro-crack densities on the mid-spans (Sides A' and B') should be lower than on the edges (Sides A and B). This was not the case. In addition, the surface ply micro-crack density on the edges did not saturate at 1000 cycles. Again, since new micro-cracks were being observed on the edge of the samples with continued cycling, theoretically if the micro-cracks had initiated at the sample edges, then to achieve equal micro-crack densities at the mid-span and edges, the cracks would have to grow across the full span (width) almost immediately after initiating. Consequently, these results suggest that edge micro-crack formation did not dominate micro-crack initiation. At least a significant amount of the surface ply micro-cracks (possibly most of them) did not initiate at the edges. Although somewhat uncommon due to the usual dominance of "edge-effect stresses," occasional references to internal cracks that do not intersect the laminate edges have been made in past work (for example [14]).

Plies	Micro-cracks / cm					
	[0/90] _{2s} edge	[0/90] _{2s} mid-span	[0/+45/-45/90] _s edge (side A)	[0/+45/-45/90] _s edge (side B)	[0/+45/-45/90] _s mid-span (side A')	[0/+45/-45/90] _s mid-span (side B')
1,8	5.81	7.59	N/A	5.97	N/A	8.15
2,7	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.07	1.91	1.05
3,5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
4,5	0.07	0.27	0.20	N/A	0.03	N/A

Table 1 Edge and mid-span micro-crack densities in standard prepreg IM7 / 5250-4 after 1000 LN₂ cycles

Plies	Micro-cracks / cm					
	[0/90] _{2s} edge	[0/90] _{2s} mid-span	[0/+45/-45/90] _s edge (side A)	[0/+45/-45/90] _s edge (side B)	[0/+45/-45/90] _s mid-span (side A')	[0/+45/-45/90] _s mid-span (side B')
1,8	8.04	8.77	N/A	5.64	N/A	6.44
2,7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.85	2.62	3.70
3,5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
4,5	0.00	0.00	0.00	N/A	0.00	N/A

Table 2 Edge and mid-span micro-crack densities in thick prepreg IM7 / 5250-4 after 1000 LN₂ cycles

The inner ply micro-cracking trends from sectioning are less consistent. Plies 2 and 7 of the [0/90]_{2s} laminate and plies 4 and 5 of the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate (both from the standard prepreg material) contained more micro-cracks on the edge than at the mid-span. However, a consistent trend was observed at the mid-span of plies 2 and 7 of the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminates where there were many more micro-cracks at the mid-span than on the edges (3 to 27 times greater micro-crack density) regardless of the ply-thickness. The location of the micro-cracks in plies 2 and 7 of the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminates was also revealing. All the micro-cracks in plies 2 and 7 were located horizontally within 1 ply thickness of a micro-crack in the adjacent surface ply (as shown in Figure 8) both at the edges *and at the mid-span*. Since the same relation between the micro-cracks in the surface and adjacent plies was observed on both Side A' and Side B', it is likely to exist on all cross-sections of the samples. Intuitively, continuous micro-cracks in the +45° ply would have appeared at random horizontal locations with no relationship to the 0° ply micro-cracks. This observation suggests a continuous micro-crack pattern for the surface plies and a discontinuous pattern for the adjacent plies as shown in Figure 9. Possibly, the surface ply micro-cracks initiated away from the edges and with continued cycling grew completely across the span of the sample. Next, at various locations along the surface ply micro-crack, micro-cracks in the +45° ply initiated and grew parallel to the fibers in the +45° ply for a short distance (less than the thickness of 2

plies) in each direction away from the surface ply micro-crack before arresting. Future work will include a more detailed mapping of the micro-crack pattern by sectioning at multiple cross-sections.

Figure 8 Micro-crack locations in plies 2 and 7

Figure 9 Proposed micro-crack pattern in surface and adjacent plies (viewed from laminate top face)

Carbon / Epoxy (IM7 / 977-2)

The IM7 / 977-2 samples were extremely resistant to micro-cracking. After 1000 cycles there were only 0.03 micro-cracks / cm in plies 1 and 8 of the $[0/+45/-45/90]_s$ laminate and 0.07 micro-cracks in plies 2 and 7 of the $[0/90]_{2s}$ laminate. The remainder of the plies in each laminate had no micro-cracks. IM7 / 977-2 resisted the severe surface ply micro-cracking observed in IM7 / 5250-4 that eventually may have led to significant micro-cracking in plies 2 and 7. The mechanical properties of this material apparently do not degrade significantly with exposure to LN_2 . For example, micro-cracks first appeared in the surface plies of the $[0/+45/-45/90]_s$ laminate after 325 cycles at a density of 0.02 micro-cracks / cm. By 1000 cycles, this micro-crack density had grown only to 0.03 micro-cracks / cm.

Carbon / Epoxy (E-beam Cured IM7 / 3K)

The micro-crack density results for the e-beam cured IM7 / 3K were heavily influenced by voids in the samples. The volume fraction of voids averaged over all plies of a sample varied from 2% to 4%. With this class of materials it is typically difficult or impossible to achieve a near-zero void content as is

possible in elevated temperature autoclave curing. Most voids were located on the ply interfaces and over 80% of the micro-cracks were an extension of a void. However, initiation of micro-cracks due to voids was balanced by the lower residual stresses at ambient temperature, which were apparent by the surface ply micro-cracks which opened much less than the micro-cracks in IM7 / 5250-4 or IM7 / 977-2. As shown in Figures 4 to 7, fewer micro-cracks formed in the surface plies than in the inner plies. This trend was likely due to the increased density of voids with increasing distance from the sample surface. Consequently, the micro-crack density in plies 1 and 8 is most representative of the damage in a particular ply of IM7 / 3K that would be present if no voids were there to assist with initiation. Interestingly, despite the presence of voids, the surface ply micro-crack density of 1.5 micro-cracks / cm in the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate after 1000 cycles was substantially lower than the 6.0 micro-cracks / cm reached by the same [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate of standard prepreg IM7 / 5250-4.

COMBINED CRYOGENIC AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURE CYCLING

A separate set of standard IM7 / 5250-4 samples were subjected to the combined LN₂ / 177 °C cycle. Although adding an elevated temperature hold to the cycle would not be expected to affect the maximum ply transverse and shear stresses achieved when submerging the samples in LN₂, the accumulation of micro-cracks was significantly affected (analogous to the trends noted by Henaff-Gardin *et al.* [13] for T300/914). For example, surface ply micro-cracks first appeared at 30 to 75 cycles in the samples subjected to the combined thermal cycle as opposed to 75 to 250 cycles for the same material cycled in LN₂ only. Similarly, the maximum micro-crack density achieved after 1000 cycles was greater with elevated temperature included than without – 2.7 times greater for [0/90]_{2S} and 2.1 times greater for [0/+45/-45/90]_s. Even more unfortunate is the increased micro-crack density in the inner plies which all developed a significant density of micro-cracks. For example, the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate had 12.53, 5.09, 2.13, and 4.92 micro-cracks/cm in plies 1 and 8, 2 and 7, 3 and 6, and 4 and 5, respectively. Furthermore, the locations of the +45° ply micro-cracks in the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate were once again within a ply thickness of the surface ply micro-cracks in the horizontal direction. Similarly, the micro-cracks in the -45° plies were adjacent to the micro-cracks in the 90° plies within a ply thickness in the horizontal direction. If the micro-crack configuration is as proposed in Figure 9, there may be an array of paths for the flow of gas (connected micro-cracks traversing the thickness of the laminate) of up to 2 micro-cracks / cm on an edge.

CONCLUSIONS

The ply-level micro-crack densities in autoclave cured IM7 / 5250-4 and IM7 / 977-2 and e-beam cured IM7 / 3K were obtained on the samples edges and at the mid-span for IM7 / 5250-4 as a function of submersion in liquid nitrogen up to 1000 times. Several significant trends were noted. Reducing the ply thickness by 30% in the IM7 / 5250-4 delayed surface ply micro-cracking by up to 200 cycles, but by 1000 cycles the surface ply micro-crack densities were approximately equal in the both [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminates, and the laminates with a reduced ply thickness had significantly greater micro-crack density in some of the inner plies. Sectioning indicated greater micro-crack densities 2.5 cm away from the sample edges in several plies of each laminate – especially plies 2 and 7 which had 3 to 27 times more micro-cracks at the mid-span than at the edge of the samples. The e-beam cured IM7 / 3K had significant micro-cracking in all plies which was almost exclusively associated with voids trapped at the ply interfaces. This association with voids masked the inherent micro-crack resistance advantage of a material that appears to have extremely low residual stresses due to processing. Finally, for IM7 / 5250-4 the addition of a hold of 5 minutes per cycle at the maximum service temperature (177 °C) increased the micro-crack density in all plies at least 2 times and after 400 cycles had produced micro-cracks in every ply of the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate. By 1000 cycles the density of micro-cracks observed on the edge of each ply was 2.13 micro-cracks / cm or more in the [0/+45/-45/90]_s laminate indicating the possibility of

a large number of gas flow paths consisting of interconnected micro-cracks through the thickness of the laminate.

These results indicate that the amount of micro-cracking in a carbon / polymer composite that is subject to degradation during LN₂ cycling may be delayed by reducing the ply thickness, but the delayed micro-cracking may be recovered less than 600 cycles later. Also, including elevated temperature in the thermal cycle of some composite materials (such as IM7 / 5250-4) can lead to a devastating increase in damage accumulation due to cycling both with respect to the density of micro-cracks and the number of plies containing micro-cracks. Finally, cryogenic cycling of composites *can* produce micro-crack densities on the sample edges that are conservative compared to the interior of the sample. Therefore, the coupon-sized flat samples with exposed edges used in this research may have value for making estimates of surface ply thermal shock resistance and a material's resistance to the continuation of surface ply micro-cracks into adjacent plies – even for structural areas removed from laminate edges, joints, and cutouts.

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